

METAL COMPLEXES OF DI-*p*-TOLYLTHIOVIOLURIC ACID

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Several metal complexes of di-*p*-tolylthiovioluric acid have been prepared. All the salts are highly coloured and appear to be metal chelates of the thiovioluric acid.

Violuric acid and its derivatives contain an oxime group, $-\overset{\ominus}{\text{C}}-\text{C}(\text{NOH})-$, through enolisation. This group induces the molecule of these compounds to form inner-complex salt. One of the most important reactions of compounds of this type is the so-called "iron-blue reaction", first observed by Whiteley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 1330).

With a view to investigating analytical applications of this important class of compounds, the author prepared a number of complexes of substituted violuric acids (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1946, 23A, 330; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1956, 15B, 245; this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 198). The present work deals with similar complexes formed by di-*p*-tolylthiovioluric acid.

Theoretical considerations and properties of these salts suggest these to be inner complexes. The acid molecule in its nitroso-enolic form (I) contains a replaceable hydrogen atom, which can be replaced by a metal atom during salt formation.

Further, the molecule contains a nitrogen atom in the 1 : 4 position with respect to the oxygen atom. By virtue of a lone pair of electrons on the nitrogen atom, it can act as a donor and form a co-ordinate link with the metal atom, effecting ring-closure. That chelation can take place readily, when the two atoms concerned in chelation are in 1 : 4 position to one another, is well known.⁷ Metallic salts of di-*p*-tolylthiovioluric acid can be represented by (III).

Alternatively, chelation can also take place through the oxygen atom of the nitroso group, which would amount to the same thing as saying that the acid reacts with the metal ions in the

oximino-ketonic form (II) and the replacement of the hydrogen atom of the oxime group would then give a six-membered ring (IV).

It is difficult to decide between the alternative structures (III) and (IV). It is interesting to note that according to Sidgwick (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 433) the co-ordinating power of N or negative oxygen O^- is roughly the same. It seems highly probable, however, that the rings in these chelates are six-membered. This would be in accordance with Pfeiffer's observations (*Angew. Chem.*, 1940, 53, 93) that a five-membered ring is more stable when it is entirely saturated, but six-membered rings become more stable in case one or more double bonds are present.

The conclusion that the metallic derivatives of di-*p*-tolylthiovioluric acid are inner complexes is further supported by their intense colour, insolubility in water, and high solubility in non-polar solvents. The evidence of colour is usually considered as almost conclusive, and intensification of colour is usually considered as an indication of chelation. In addition to the above evidence on the basis of which chelate formation has been inferred, stable compounds of a large number of metals have been isolated in the solid state. From the results of analysis of these compounds, conclusions can be drawn concerning the arrangement of the co-ordinated groups around the central ion. We have observed that in some cases the co-ordination requirements of the metal atoms are not fulfilled in spite of chelation on account of the valency requirements of the metal atoms concerned. In view of the fact that the molecule of di-*p*-tolylthiovioluric acid contains a replaceable hydrogen atom, the number of molecules of the acid, which would react with one atom of the metal, should be equal to the valency of the metal atom concerned. The acid molecule as a whole acts as a bidentate chelate radical, and thus the co-ordination number of the metal atom will be equal to twice its valency in these compounds. This would mean that in many cases the co-ordination number of the metal atoms would be less than that expected from their behaviour in other co-ordination compounds. This type of behaviour is exhibited in several other cases, e.g., in the cobalt salt of ethyltetramethylpyrromethene-4 : 4'-dicarboxylic acid (Porter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 368). Alternatively, it is more likely that the remaining co-ordination positions in these complexes are occupied by water molecules, or even the anions present in the solution. Basing on the results of analysis of these compounds, which would not be greatly altered by the presence or absence of water molecules or anions within the complex (because of the high molecular weights of these complexes), it is not possible at present to draw definite conclusions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Di-*p*-tolylthiovioluric acid was synthesised by the method of Dutt *et al.* (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1936, 8A, 145). Di-*p*-tolylthiourea, obtained from *p*-toluidine and CS_2 , was condensed with malonic acid to yield di-*p*-tolylthio-barbituric acid from which the corresponding violuric acid was obtained by the action of nitrous acid.

TABLE I

Properties and analyses of metal complexes.

Salt.	Colour.	Decomp. temp.	λ_{max} .	% Sulphur.		% Metal.		Metal: acid.
				Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	
Silver	Apple green	110	..	6.96	6.93	23.45	23.44	1:1
Lead	Greyish brown	184	4624 μ	7.02	6.98	22.74	22.71	1:2
Mercurous	Pink	268	..	5.79	5.73	36.32	36.28	1:1
Mercuric	Pale yellow	204	..	7.07	7.06	22.17	22.16	1:2
Bismuth	Orange-brown	> 350°	4345	7.58	7.59	16.52	16.52	1:3
Copper	Dark brown	186	4700	8.33	8.32	8.28	8.29	1:2
Cadmium	Pinkish orange	255	4324	7.83	7.80	13.76	13.75	1:2
Antimony(III)	Orange	201°	4248	8.15	8.11	10.33	10.30	1:3
Stannous	Yellow	> 350°	4200	7.76	7.77	14.42	14.40	1:2
Stannic	Deep orange	> 350	..	8.38	8.39	7.77	7.71	1:4
Gold	Brownish yellow	155	..	7.66	7.65	15.74	15.72	1:3
Platinum	Yellowish brown	178	4800	7.98	7.98	12.17	12.19	1:4
Cerous	Pinkish grey	232	4440	8.02	8.10	11.71	11.69	1:3
Ceric	Reddish brown	> 350	5305	8.26	8.24	9.05	8.97	1:4
Thorium	Grey	> 350	4392	7.80	7.81	14.15	14.15	1:4
Ferrous	Deep blue	164	6202	8.42	8.41	7.35	7.35	1:2
Ferric	Dark green.	172	6500	8.63	8.63	5.01	4.91	1:3
Aluminium	Greyish yellow	195	..	8.86	9.01	2.49	2.50	1:3
Chromium	Brownish orange	199°	4318	8.66	8.64	4.69	4.67	1:3
Vanadium(III)	Orange-brown	159	4732	8.67	8.65	4.60	4.58	1:3
Vanadyl	Orange	194	4850	8.30	8.31	6.60	6.62	1:2
Beryllium	Greyish yellow	187	4215	8.97	8.94	1.26	1.23	1:2
Titanyl	Brownish orange	193	4202	8.33	8.32	6.23	6.22	1:2
Zirconium	Reddish brown	180	4268	8.53	8.49	6.08	6.03	1:4
Uranyl	Yellow	241	4296	6.57	6.55	24.44	24.43	1:2
Lanthanum	Pinkish brown	> 350	..	8.03	8.01	11.62	11.66	1:3
Cobalt	Dark brown	247°	4578	8.38	8.32	7.72	7.69	1:2
Nickel	Yellowish grey	> 350	4752	8.39	8.36	7.69	7.65	1:2
Manganese	Slate-coloured	254	4367	8.43	8.41	7.23	7.22	1:2
Zinc	Grey	246°	..	8.32	8.32	8.49	8.48	1:2
Calcium	Pink	> 350	4356	8.60	8.61	5.38	5.37	1:2
Strontium	Deep pink	> 350	..	8.08	7.94	11.06	11.03	1:2
Barium	Deep pink	> 350	..	7.60	7.59	16.32	16.3	1:2
Magnesium	Brownish orange	> 350	..	8.78	8.74	3.33	3.32	1:2
Ammonium	Bluish grey	164	5290	8.64	8.62	..	..	1:1
Lithium	Orange-red	264°	4500	8.91	8.89	1.93	1.90	1:1
Sodium	Light greenish	241°	..	8.53	8.49	..	..	1:1
Potassium	Green	230°	..	8.18	8.21	..	..	1:1

Metallic Salts of Di-p-tolylthiovioluric Acid.—The ammonium salt was obtained by the addition of an excess of ammonium hydroxide to the acid, and evaporating the solution to dryness on a water bath when the ammonium salt was left behind. Alkali metal salts were similarly obtained

by dissolving the acid in minimum quantity of strong alkali solution. The solution was evaporated to dryness and the impure alkali metal salt was purified by crystallisation from water.

Salts of other metals were obtained by adding a saturated solution of the ammonium salt in water to a saturated solution of the salt of the metal concerned. The insoluble metallic salts were thrown down as precipitates. Chlorides or nitrates of metals were used in most cases.

The precipitates of the salts, thus obtained, were washed with water till free of impurities, and metal and sulphur contents were determined, the latter by oxidation to sulphate and by weighing as barium sulphate. Majority of the metals in the complexes were estimated by ignition of weighed quantities of complexes and weighing the oxides of the metals, which were left behind. In those cases, where the metal did not form an oxide of definite composition, the residue was dissolved, and the metal reprecipitated in a form suitable for its gravimetric estimation.

All the metallic salts of di-*p*-tolylthiovioluric acid are highly coloured, crystalline in nature, and are stable in the solid state as well as in organic solvents. Excepting the alkali metal salts, these are insoluble in water and soluble in organic solvents, e.g., acetone, ether and dioxan. Aqueous solutions of these salts respond to most of the tests for the corresponding cations showing that there is some dissociation in most cases. On heating the salts melt with decomposition. The silver salt is photosensitive and becomes black in about three days in diffused light. The absorption maxima of a number of these compounds were determined with the help of a constant deviation spectrograph (Hilger) and in some cases by a spectrophotometer (Unicam, S.P. 600 model). Results of analysis and some properties of the salts are recorded in Table I.

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